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“Druggability and Genetic Variability of the Catalytic and Allosteric Sites of SARS-CoV-2 nsp14 Across Coronaviruses and SARS-CoV-2 Samples”

Introduction:

Coronaviruses are RNA viruses. Viral RNA molecules are 5' capped to mimic host RNA and evade the immune system. Non-structural protein 14 (nsp14) is a bifunctional enzyme that comprises an RNA cap guanine N7-methyltransferase (N7-MTase) and a 3'-5' exoribonuclease (ExoN) activity. Nsp14 binds to nsp10 to form the nsp14-nsp10 complex. The presence of nsp10 is important for nsp14 to have its ExoN activity. (Bouvet et al., 2012 <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1201130109>). The nsp14-nsp10 complex also catalyzes the transfer of a methyl group from S-adenosylmethionine (SAM) to guanosine-P3-adenosine-5',5'-triphosphate (GpppA or G3A). The replication fidelity of SARS-CoV-1 has been linked with nsp14 ExoN activity. The capping function of nsp14 is important for viral mRNA translation and evading host defense. Therefore, nsp14-nsp10 could be a potential target for anti-SARS-CoV-1, anti-SARS-Cov-2 and more broadly anti-coronavirus drugs.

In the absence of a structure for SARS-CoV-2 nsp14, we used the SARS-CoV-1 structure to map and analyze binding pockets. The crystal structure of the SARS-CoV-1 nsp14-nsp10 dimer was solved (Ma et al., 2015) and can be used as a model of the SARS-CoV-2 protein, as both proteins share 95% sequence identity and are 100% identical at the methyltransferase catalytic site. (<https://www.pnas.org/content/112/30/9436>)

Methods and Results:

Step 1: Assessing the druggability of SARS-CoV-1 nsp14 structure.

Using IcmPocketFinder (Molsoft, San Diego) and a crystal structure of the nsp14-nsp10 dimer bound to SAH (S-adenosyl-homocystein, the de-methylated version of SAM) and GpppA (PDB: 5C8S), two well-defined pockets are found at the surface of nsp14: the methyltransferase active site (blue) and an allosteric site (red) as shown in figure 1.

Using SiteMap (Halgren 2019) both pockets are predicted to be druggable (Dscores of 0.99 and 1.05 respectively):

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Figure 1. The druggability of nsp14.

The remainder of the report provides an overview of the amino acid variability at both the catalytic and allosteric sites.

Step 2. Determining the residues that line nsp14 catalytic and allosteric pockets.

We identified the surrounding residues of both pockets. The catalytic pocket of nsp14 is surrounded by 40 amino acids: V287, R289, V290, W292, N306, C309, R310, Q313, D331, I332, G333, N334, P335, K336, I338, K339, C340, D352, A353, Q354, L366, F367, Y368, L383, W385, N386, C387, N388, V389, R400, F401, Y420, N422, K423, H424, F426, H427, T428, P429, F506. The allosteric pocket is surrounded by 28 residues: V83, R84, A85, W86, I87, S112, T113, T173, L174, L177, V263, H264, I275, R278, C279, V282, T403, R404, L406, S407, N408, N410, L411, P412, G413, G416, S418, L419.

Figure 2. The catalytic pocket of nsp14 (MTase site) has 40 surrounding sidechains.

Figure 3. The allosteric pocket of nsp14 has 28 surrounding sidechains.

Step 3. Making diversity dendrograms for sequences of the Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera entries in UniProt database.

We conducted a broad survey of viral proteins from Alpha- and Betacoronaviruses to identify the most conserved druggable sites. By integrating variability and druggability data, we can then infer the most promising strategies for developing broad-spectrum antiviral small-molecule inhibitors. This analysis can be valuable in the context of the emergence of future coronaviruses from circulating viral strains in bat reservoir species. We looked at twenty-seven reviewed nsp14 sequences from UniProt, where six belong to Alphacoronavirus genus entries, and twenty-one belong to the Betacoronavirus genus. We then assessed the variability of amino acid lining the nsp14 catalytic MTase site and its allosteric site by performing multiple sequence alignment.

We made diversity dendrograms focusing on the 40 sidechains of the catalytic site (figure 2) and the 28 sidechains of the allosteric site (figure 3) from step2.

16 out of 40 residues lining the MTase active site are not conserved and 24 residues were shown to be identical which translates to 60% sequence identity at this site. Here are the 24 identical residues among the Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera entries: W292, N306, R310, D331, G333, N334, P335, K336, D352, Y368, W385, N386, C387, N388, V389, R400, F401, Y420, N422, H424, F426, H427, T428, F506. Here is a list of non-identical residues among the Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera entries: V287, R289, V290, C309, Q313, I332, I338, K339, C340, A353, Q354, L366, F367, L383, K423, P429.

16 out of 28 (57%) residues lining allosteric site are not conserved and 12 residues were shown to be identical which translates to 43% sequence identity at this site. Here are the 12 identical residues among the Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera entries: R84, W86, S112, H264, R278, C279, T403, R404, L411, G413, G416, L419. Here is a list of non-identical residues among the Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera entries: V83, A85, I87, T113, T173, L174, L177, V263, I275, V282, L406, S407, N408, N410, P412, S418.

Figure 4. The diversity dendrogram of nsp14 catalytic MTase site residues across 27 Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera UniProt entries.

Figure 5. The diversity dendrogram of nsp14 allosteric site residues across 27 Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera UniProt entries.

Step 4. Map variations observed among Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera entries onto nsp14 structure.

Figure 6 and 7 are the color-coded representations of nsp14 to highlight the identical and non-identical residues among the entries of the Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera based on the diversity dendrogram in step 3.

Figure 6. Mapping the genetic variations at nsp14 catalytic site among Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera entries onto nsp14 structure.

Figure 7. Mapping the genetic variations at nsp14 allosteric site among Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera entries onto nsp14 structure.

Step 5: Assessing the genetic variability of catalytic and allosteric sites of nsp14 among SARS-CoV-2 samples.

In our next step, we wanted to look at the genetic diversity of NSP14 among SARS-CoV-2 samples from COVID-19 patients. Nicola De Maio, our collaborator from European Bioinformatics Institute (EBI) looked at more than 15000 SARS-CoV-2 samples to find the variants at its catalytic and allosteric sites.

Below in Table 1, you can see the nine non-synonymous variants at the MTase site and eight at the allosteric site of nsp14 that Nicola observed among the SARS-CoV-2 samples.

Site	Wild Type amino acid	Amino acid counts, different alleles are separated by commas	observed nucleotide alleles at first codon position	observed nucleotide alleles at second codon position	observed nucleotide alleles at third codon position	Description
Mtase	V287	F(3),V(15871)	t(3),g(15871)	t(15875)	t(15875)	3 variants from USA from a single mutation
Mtase	R289	C(9),R(15865)	c(15865),t(9)	g(15874)	t(15874)	9 variants from Europe from 3 mutation events,
Mtase	V290	F(4),V(15869)	t(4),g(15869)	t(15874)	t(15874)	4 variants from Greece, Wales and Chile, 4 different mutation events.
Mtase	N306	S(1),N(15863)	a(15864)	a(15863),g(1)	t(15864)	Variant from Kazakhstan EPI_ISL_435047
Mtase	A353	A(15873),V(1)	g(15875)	c(15873),t(1)	a(15875)	Variant from England EPI_ISL_443361
Mtase	Q354	Q(15872),H(3)	c(15875)	a(15875)	t(3),g(15872)	3 variants from USA and Wales from a single mutation event.
Mtase	L366	L(15874),F(1)	c(1),t(15874)	t(15875)	a(15873),t(1),g(1)	Codon CTA from Saudi Arabia EPI_ISL_437747, Codon TTG from USA EPI_ISL_416702, Codon TTT (F variant) from USA EPI_ISL_418080
Mtase	C387	Y(1),C(15874)	t(15875)	a(1),g(15874)	c(15875)	1 Y variant from Denmark EPI_ISL_429565
Mtase	P429	P(14875),L(1)	c(14887)	c(14882),t(1)	a(14885)	1 L variant from USA EPI_ISL_422988
Allosteric	T113	I(4),T(15870)	a(15875)	c(15870),t(4)	a(15875)	4 I variants from Iran, Denmark, England and UAE, from 3 mutation events
Allosteric	T173	I(2),T(15873)	a(15875)	c(15873),t(2)	a(15875)	2 I variants from England from one mutation event.
Allosteric	L177	L(15860),F(13)	c(15860),t(13)	t(15875)	c(15870),t(5)	13 F variants from China, Canada, England, Russia, Taiwan, from 7 different

						mutation events. 5 synonymous variants from Denmark, England, France, Netherlands, from 4 mutation events.
Allosteric	V263	F(2),V(15870)	t(2),g(15871)	t(15872)	c(15866),t(7)	2 F variants from USA, from 1 mutation event. 7 synonymous variants from Luxembourg, Netherlands and China, from 3 mutation events.
Allosteric	I275	I(15869),T(5)	a(15874)	c(5),t(15869)	c(15874)	5 T variants from USA, Canada and England from 3 mutation events
Allosteric	R278	S(1),R(15873)	a(15874)	g(15874)	t(1),g(15873)	1 S variant from Wales EPI_ISL_419399
Allosteric	P412	P(15359),S(2)	c(15360),t(2)	c(15362)	t(15361)	2 S variants from Portugal and England from 1 mutation event.
Allosteric	G416	S(1),G(15010)	a(1),g(15141)	g(15125)	t(15012)	1 S variant from Turkey, EPI_ISL_437319.

Table 1. Non-synonymous variants at the catalytic and allosteric sites of nsp14 among SARS-CoV-2 samples.

Step 6: Predicting the effect of mutations from SARS-CoV-2 samples on the binding of endogenous ligands, the cofactor SAH and the G3A, with nsp14.

Since there is no structure of nsp14 in complex with inhibitors, we evaluated the effect of these mutations on the co-crystallized endogenous ligands SAH and G3A. Chemical inhibitors should occupy the same site, and probably mimic several interactions made by endogenous ligands, which is why we use this structure as a first approximation. Mutations predicted to penalize SAH, or G3A, will not necessarily penalize the binding of future inhibitors (though they are likely to).

Difference in Gibbs binding energy is calculated with ICM for the methyltransferase site (we estimate the precision of the prediction to be around 2 kcal/mol - Schapira et al). These mutations span the methyltransferase site of SAH and G3A.

INX	Wild Type Residue	Mutant	distance to SAH	distance to G3A	Ligand	ddGbind
1	V287	F	6.985	9.716	SAH	0

2	R289	C	3.126	8.885	SAH	0
3	V290	F	3.218	5.945	SAH	0.7
4	N306	S	9.001	1.635	G3A	-2.1
5	A353	V	2.462	10.4	SAH	3.4
6	Q354	H	2.189	9.998	SAH	0.8
7	L366	F	2.766	13.43	SAH	0.3
8	C387	Y	2.67	3.899	SAH	-1.1
9	P429	L	6.546	5.033	G3A	-0.2

Table 2. The energy calculations for the SARS-CoV-2 non-synonymous mutations observed among SARS-CoV-2 samples of the residues lining the catalytic pocket of nsp14. The energy unit is kcal/mol.

Step 6: Predicting the effect of all possible mutations on endogenous ligands binding.

Lastly, we assessed the effect of all possible mutations at the sidechains lining the catalytic site of nsp14 that would affect G3A or SAH-binding. Table 3 below shows all possible mutations and the ddGbind values corresponding to each. To determine the ligand that should be considered for ddGbind calculation, we used the distance function in ICM to measure which of the two ligands (G3A, SAM) is closer to each of the sidechains lining nsp14 catalytic site. Based on that selection of the ligand, all possible mutations were modeled in ICM, and the change in Gibbs free energy in ligand binding was calculated and presented in Table 3.

It is likely that the residues of the rows with green color do not make optimal interactions with SAH or G3A substrate. This is reflected in the slight and non-significant lowering of ddGbind values of these residues (mutations are stabilizing) and hence the green color. Inhibitors could potentially make strong interactions (better than SAH or G3A) with wild-type sidechains at these positions. On the other hand, the sidechains whose mutations are shown in orange are likely the positions where nsp14 better interact with SAH or G3A. As a result, the mutations of those sidechains are predicted to penalize SAH- and G3A-binding significantly and hence the orange color.

In the absence of structures in complex with inhibitors, the predicted effect of these mutations is on the binding of endogenous ligands. The effect could be different on the binding of future inhibitors, especially if inhibitors do not mimic receptor-ligand interactions observed with SAH or G3A.

Residue Number	WT	Ligand	Mutant Residue																			
			gly	ala	val	leu	ile	pro	cys	met	ser	thr	phe	tyr	trp	asn	gln	asp	glu	his	lys	arg
287	V	SAH	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.0	-0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	-0.1	-0.2	-0.2	-0.1	0.2	-0.1
289	R	SAH	0.0	0.2	-0.2	-0.2	-0.5	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.4	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.0
290	V	SAH	0.8	0.5	0.0	0.8	0.8	-0.3	0.9	-0.1	1.8	0.9	0.7	0.6	0.7	1.7	0.6	1.2	2.1	0.7	0.9	0.7
292	W	SAH	-2.9	-2.7	2.8	2.6	-2.6	-2.8	-2.6	-2.3	2.7	2.8	-1.8	0.0	0.0	-2.4	2.5	2.3	-2.1	-0.4	-1.7	-2.1
306	N	G3A	1.2	0.4	11.3	23.7	-1.2	0.6	-2.4	7.6	-2.1	11.0	7.7	9.8	24.7	0.0	-12.4	14.5	14.5	8.1	-3.7	-6.0
309	C	G3A	1.7	2.6	-10.4	15.6	19.4	0.7	0.0	20.2	-2.1	-4.5	-5.6	-4.8	-1.2	9.5	3.0	8.2	18.6	-0.3	27.6	21.8
310	R	G3A	1.3	-0.7	10.0	1.7	8.6	-3.0	-2.3	2.9	-8.3	-1.9	12.3	19.1	5.9	3.7	-0.6	2.5	2.4	1.6	-0.5	0.0
313	Q	G3A	0.1	-0.2	-0.5	-0.5	-14.8	0.2	-0.2	0.0	-0.9	-0.5	-0.7	-0.6	-0.2	0.0	0.0	1.6	2.2	-1.2	-0.1	0.7
311	D	SAH	-2.0	-2.2	-2.1	-1.3	-2.2	39.5	-2.2	2.1	-2.5	-2.4	-2.8	-1.8	-1.8	1.6	-1.9	0.0	-1.8	-1.5	-0.4	0.7
332	I	SAH	1.7	2.0	0.6	1.4	0.0	15.7	1.7	1.6	2.1	1.0	2.0	2.3	1.9	1.6	1.6	4.1	4.3	1.7	1.3	0.3
333	G	SAH	0.0	-0.8	2.5	20.1	2.8	153.5	4.1	7.3	-1.6	4.0	70.6	58.8	86.2	10.9	10.3	17.8	19.1	54.8	39.3	17.9
334	N	SAH	-1.8	-1.3	-2.5	-1.0	-2.6	39.5	-2.0	0.2	-2.6	-0.3	-0.5	-0.8	-0.3	0.0	-0.8	2.4	1.9	-1.1	-1.6	-0.9
335	P	SAH	2.9	2.6	3.2	4.0	6.7	0.0	3.7	3.4	2.1	2.6	79.8	34.7	40.8	0.5	5.2	11.5	10.4	9.1	15.1	-5.3
336	K	G3A	-17.2	-17.7	-17.2	-19.4	-17.3	-18.3	-17.8	-16.8	-16.9	-17.0	-18.9	-19.2	-17.9	-18.1	-21.2	-16.1	-18.3	-17.8	0.0	-22.2
338	I	G3A	-5.4	-4.3	14.7	5.1	0.0	-5.6	-12.7	7.0	-1.3	0.6	-4.4	-14.5	-14.5	-0.6	-4.2	-5.3	-1.4	-15.5	-8.8	-1.7
339	K	G3A	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	0.2	0.0	8.3	0.1	0.0	-0.1	0.3	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	0.5	-0.1	-0.1	0.1	-0.3	0.0	0.0
340	C	SAH	-0.3	-0.5	0.5	0.3	0.0	0.3	0.0	-0.4	-0.4	-0.2	0.3	0.1	1.6	-0.3	0.3	0.2	0.1	-0.4	-0.6	-0.8
352	D	SAH	-0.5	-1.5	-0.8	-0.3	-1.8	44.8	-5.0	-2.2	-6.3	-1.2	63.0	63.7	25.4	-6.2	2.6	0.0	3.4	16.6	10.1	53.9
353	A	SAH	1.5	0.0	3.4	0.9	2.3	13.6	1.4	10.2	0.2	1.5	103.7	34.4	2.5	2.9	1.5	3.7	6.9	2.9	-1.7	-6.1
354	Q	SAH	1.3	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.3	99.5	0.1	0.1	0.4	0.1	0.8	0.8	0.0	-3.3	0.0	2.0	0.8	-0.1	-0.1	-0.2
366	L	SAH	1.3	1.5	1.0	0.0	0.6	1.1	-1.0	-0.7	1.2	1.1	0.3	0.2	-1.6	1.0	-0.4	1.1	3.0	1.1	0.7	1.2
367	F	SAH	5.1	4.6	2.6	1.3	2.4	56.7	2.5	2.2	4.2	3.0	0.0	1.0	-0.9	2.2	2.2	3.3	2.6	-0.1	1.8	2.5
368	Y	SAH	1.4	0.0	-0.3	0.2	-0.3	20.2	0.2	0.0	0.2	0.5	-0.1	0.0	0.4	0.2	-0.7	0.3	1.2	0.1	-0.3	-0.3
383	L	SAH	-1.3	-1.2	-1.1	0.0	-1.1	7.8	-0.1	0.1	-0.7	-0.8	0.8	1.1	1.7	0.2	0.2	1.7	2.4	0.7	-0.1	-0.1
385	W	SAH	-0.3	0.2	-0.2	-0.9	0.0	15.1	-0.3	-0.2	0.4	0.7	0.6	0.3	0.0	0.7	0.4	0.3	1.5	0.8	0.3	0.3
386	N	G3A	7.2	8.1	18.9	4.5	25.1	7.2	6.4	26.5	7.4	56.7	9.3	8.4	2.4	0.0	22.0	4.8	17.8	0.6	-0.4	39.0
387	C	SAH	3.2	0.4	4.8	-2.2	2.4	16.1	0.0	3.6	1.8	1.5	0.2	-1.1	-0.8	-1.7	-3.5	7.6	4.9	0.2	-6.4	-6.7
388	N	SAH	0.0	-0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2	-1.5	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.0	-0.2	-0.2	0.0	0.4	0.1	0.0	0.0	-0.2	0.1	0.3
389	V	SAH	1.1	1.0	0.0	-1.4	-1.8	33.7	-0.9	-1.4	1.1	0.6	-7.4	-5.6	5.8	-0.6	-2.3	4.8	2.1	-6.7	-3.9	-4.7
400	R	G3A	0.8	0.2	1.1	1.3	1.3	3.5	1.3	1.2	1.6	1.5	0.9	0.6	2.2	2.2	1.3	1.9	1.7	1.3	1.2	0.0
401	F	G3A	-5.1	2.1	8.4	2.6	10.2	3.9	1.9	2.1	2.1	3.4	0.0	-3.1	-0.3	2.1	15.4	4.1	1.9	0.4	-9.5	-0.7
420	Y	G3A	2.8	1.9	0.5	0.6	1.4	37.4	1.5	1.0	1.2	0.3	-0.3	0.0	-7.1	1.9	-7.2	4.6	2.1	0.8	1.6	-1.2
422	N	G3A	2.7	1.1	0.0	14.9	0.7	17.3	0.1	0.3	0.4	-1.0	0.1	0.3	1.4	0.0	-1.8	2.1	1.9	1.7	20.6	3.8
423	K	G3A	-0.3	0.3	1.0	-2.7	-2.5	6.6	-2.5	0.0	3.6	-3.4	-1.8	-6.5	5.3	-1.4	7.2	0.9	4.9	-4.9	0.0	0.0
424	H	G3A	-2.6	-1.8	-0.6	0.6	1.5	0.0	-0.7	1.8	-1.3	-1.0	1.3	1.5	2.2	-0.8	0.3	0.8	7.7	-0.4	5.5	1.6
426	F	G3A	2.7	0.9	4.1	11.7	10.5	8.4	1.5	11.8	3.4	6.6	0.0	6.2	0.8	1.9	26.8	9.3	22.3	-1.9	39.6	-2.5
427	H	G3A	0.0	0.1	-0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.6	-0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.3	0.0	0.0	-0.2	0.1	0.1	0.6	-0.3	-0.2	-0.1
428	T	G3A	1.2	-0.4	2.0	22.4	22.2	6.5	6.6	24.1	-11.5	0.0	37.8	87.7	-6.2	5.8	5.4	1.0	36.5	39.0	40.4	54.2
429	P	G3A	0.0	0.0	-0.3	-0.2	-0.2	0.0	-0.2	-0.2	0.0	-0.1	0.1	0.1	-0.1	-0.1	-0.2	-0.2	-0.2	-0.3	-0.3	-0.5

Table 3. The energy matrix of mutations of the 40 residues lining the catalytic pocket of nsp14 of SARS-CoV-2. The energy unit is kcal/mol.

Table 3 color-coding based on ddGbind value (X) in Kcal/mol
X > 10.0
4.0 > X > 10.0
2.0 > X > 4.0
-2.0 > X > 2.0
-4.0 > X > -2.0
-10.0 > X > -4.0
-10.0 > X

Conclusion:

The MTase site of nsp14 is both more druggable and more conserved across coronaviruses than its allosteric site. Hence our findings encourage the design of a broad-spectrum inhibitor against the catalytic site of nsp14.

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